

Primer: Managing Complex Data Analysis Workflows

[Peter Degen](#), [Christian Meesters](#), [Gorka Fraga-González](#), [Samuel Pawel](#), [Fabio Molo](#)

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Motivation

A typical data analysis workflow (Fig. 1) consists of input files (data, configuration files) that are processed with various tools (software packages, custom scripts) to generate output files (summary tables, figures, or even an entire manuscript). If the workflow is simple, one might be tempted to manage this workflow “manually” (e.g., individually calling scripts from the command line) or by writing a short Bash script that sequentially performs all necessary tasks.

Figure 1: Example data analysis workflow. Figure sourced from [The Turing Way](#) handbook under a CC-BY license.

However, as the number of files and processing steps increases, this approach quickly becomes cumbersome and error-prone. Further complications arise if individual processing steps require different virtual environments or need to be run in specialized computing setups (workstation, cluster, cloud). For this reason, numerous *workflow managers* have been developed to streamline this process and improve the [sustainability](#) of research analysis. This primer introduces these tools to analysts who are faced with increasingly complex data analysis pipelines or who wish to improve their management of such pipelines.

Although features and design philosophies differ between systems, common benefits of workflow managers include the following:

- **Dependency resolution:** The workflow manager automatically tracks dependencies between input files, processing steps, and their corresponding outputs. Thus, the programmer does not need to explicitly specify the execution order. Rather, the workflow manager determines the execution order to ensure that the desired output is generated.
- **Selective rebuilding and checkpointing:** If a file is modified externally, the workflow manager will rerun only the steps affected by the changes. This can be achieved by tracking metadata such as file modification timestamps or checksums.
- **Error recovery:** Allows continuation of the workflow if one of the steps fails, with fine-grained conditional logic to handle errors.
- **Concurrency and parallelization:** Workflow managers simplify the concurrent execution of independent processing steps, such as running many simulations with different parameter configurations. Tools within each step can further leverage parallelism (e.g., multithreading), allowing efficient use of computational resources with minimal programming effort.

- **Reproducibility and containerization:** Built-in support for running individual steps in different virtual environments and/or [software containers](#). Some workflow managers provide a simple way to containerize the entire workflow.
- **Scalability:** Built-in integration with job schedulers/executors running on specialized compute environments (workstation, cluster, cloud).
- **Flexibility:** Processing steps can be dynamically generated using wild cards and pattern matching. Integration with powerful general-purpose languages such as Python enables a high degree of customization to construct file paths, validate configuration settings, and implement conditional logic.
- **Readability and standardization:** The workflow constitutes an explicit record of how scripts are used and what their inputs and outputs are. Programmers are compelled to structure their code and directories in a tidy and user-independent manner. Workflows can be easily shared and reused through workflow registries.
- **Modularity:** Workflows can be broken down into reusable sub-workflows, enhancing readability, maintainability, and extensibility.
- **Quality-of-life features:** Various extra features that improve usability and transparency; for example, generating HTML reports with detailed data provenance (software versions, arguments), tracking resource usage (CPU, memory, time), visualizing the dependency graph, integration with version control systems, and much more.

We proceed by introducing Make, a foundational automation tool that is still widely used today, followed by two popular, advanced workflow managers: Snakemake and Nextflow. Minimal code examples are available on [GitLab](#) and [Zenodo](#). A comparison of the three tools can be found in Table 1 in the Appendix. Moving forward, a basic familiarity with the command line and programmatic data analysis (e.g., in R or Python) is assumed.

A simple workflow with Make

Make (Feldman, 1979) is a build automation tool with numerous derivatives; among them, [GNU Make](#) serves as the standard implementation on Linux and macOS, while Windows users can install it through [Windows Subsystem for Linux](#) or directly using [Make for Windows](#). Although originally developed to build workflows for compiling code, Make can also be used for generic pipelines that produce output files from input files. To implement a workflow in Make, the user writes a *Makefile* that defines the workflow using *rules* that build *targets* from *dependencies* using *recipes* (shell commands):

```
1 # Generic Makefile rule
2 target: dependencies
3     recipe
```

As a toy example, we will consider a workflow that consists of two steps:

1. Call a Python script that processes two samples and merges the results to `merged.csv`.
2. Call another Python script that takes `merged.csv` and creates `figure.pdf`.

The corresponding Makefile might look as follows:

```
1 # Rule 1
2 merged.csv: merge_samples.py sample1.csv sample2.csv
3     python merge_samples.py -in sample1.csv sample2.csv -out merged.csv
4
5 # Rule 2
6 figure.pdf: plot_figure.py merged.csv
7     python plot_figure.py -in merged.csv -out figure.pdf
```

In our example, both scripts accept file paths directly from the command line using the `-in` and `-out` flags. The final output `figure.pdf` can be created by invoking the command `make figure.pdf`. In particular, the order of rules in the Makefile is irrelevant, as Make resolves dependencies automatically. When the command is invoked, Make registers `plot_figure.py` and `merged.csv` as dependencies of `figure.pdf` and thus checks if the files can be found in the working directory or constructed from other rules. This process results in a chain of dependencies that take the form of a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG), representing all the rules Make needs to run to satisfy the build target. The DAG of our toy example is shown in Fig. A in the Appendix. Moreover, the `make` command can be invoked with the `-n` option to display the rules that are scheduled to run, without actually running them (also known as a *dry run*). This is useful for basic soundness checks before running resource-heavy workflows.

Additionally, if any files are updated externally, Make uses their last modified timestamps to decide which targets need to be rebuilt on subsequent runs. This is perhaps best illustrated using a decision tree (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Conceptual decision tree of a workflow rule.

Improving our Make workflow with “all” and wildcards

If the `make` command is invoked without any arguments, Make by default builds the first target in the Makefile. In our toy example, this would be `merged.csv`, but this is typically not the behavior we want. We could reverse the order of the rules in our Makefile, but this makes it less human-readable and restricts our workflow to one final target. A standard trick is therefore to create a so-called *phony target* at the top of the Makefile, conventionally called `all`, which depends on all final output(s):

```

1 # Phony target to kickstart the construction of the DAG
2 all: figure.pdf
3
4 # Remaining rules below
  
```

Now, when `make` is invoked, Make will build the DAG starting from the `all` rule, which has a phony target rather than a real output file. However, since this target still depends on `figure.pdf`, Make will try to satisfy this dependency and trigger a chain reaction of rules that results in our desired workflow.

Another shortcoming of our original Makefile is that we have hard-coded the number of samples in the rule that creates `merged.pdf`. We can rectify this by using the `*` wildcard character known from shell scripting. However, since Make does not expand wildcards directly in dependency lists, we must define a separate variable using the `wildcard` function as follows:

```
1 SAMPLES := $(wildcard sample*.csv)
2 merged.csv: merge_samples.py $(SAMPLES)
3 python merge_samples.py -in $(SAMPLES) -out merged.csv
```

The skeptical reader might wonder why we don't simply modify the Python script so that it dynamically finds all input samples by itself. While feasible, we would lose Make's ability to track the timestamps of files and selectively rebuild only those targets affected by changes. For more complex workflows, this selective rebuilding can result in significant time savings. Similarly, we note that it is not required to list the Python script as a dependency (for the human reader, it is already evident from the recipe), but we choose to do so to enable selective rebuilding if the Python script is modified.

To dive deeper into Make and learn more about phony targets, pattern rules, automatic variables, path substitution, and more, we refer to the chapter [Reproducibility with Make](#) from The Turing Way handbook ([Community, 2021](#)).

Use cases and limitations of Make

As a build automation tool, Make was not developed with complex, data-driven workflows in mind. A better alternative use case for Make is [Dynamic Reporting](#) ([Peikert and Brandmaier, 2021](#); [Hofmann et al., 2023](#)), where Make serves as a "report automation tool" to integrate the generation of figures/tables directly into the final manuscript (Fig. 1). As manuscript writing is an iterative process, we are typically limited to working with small or pre-processed data sets from which figures can be generated in a matter of seconds. However, if we are dealing with raw data that require complex, resource-intensive processing steps, we will run into limitations that render Make less than ideal. As an example, we will consider the following (still fairly simple) workflow:

1. Perform 1'000 simulations with different configurations, each of which takes considerable time to complete. The simulation program is installed in virtual environment A.
2. Process each complete simulation with a special tool that is installed in virtual environment B.

Due to the large number of simulations, we probably want to use a job scheduler such as [SLURM](#) to run the workflow on a high-performance computing cluster (HPC). We could write a Make rule that calls a Bash script to send the jobs, but ideally we want a manager that natively (or via plugins) supports non-local platforms and offers features such as job monitoring and precise run configuration. Similarly, for the second rule, we could manually switch the virtual environment using a shell command in the recipe, but would prefer a manager that natively supports virtual environments and containers. Looking beyond our toy example, more realistic workflows may process hundreds of GB of data, produce thousands of files, and involve branching paths and dozens of specialized tools (see Figs. [B](#) and [C](#) in the Appendix for two examples).

Advanced workflows

To overcome the shortcomings of Make for data-driven workflows, we now introduce two powerful alternatives: Snakemake and Nextflow. Although these tools are particularly popular in the bioinformatics community, they are domain-agnostic and can be used in any data-intensive discipline such as image analysis, cheminformatics, or [high-energy physics](#).¹

¹Incidentally, in March 2025, CERN hosted a [Snakemake Hackathon](#).

Snakemake

As the name implies, [Snakemake](#) (Mölder et al., 2021) is a Python-based workflow manager with a design philosophy inspired by Make. However, whereas Make is a build automation tool that can be repurposed for data analysis, Snakemake is explicitly designed to create reproducible, portable, and scalable data-driven workflows. Instead of a Makefile, the user writes a *Snakefile* with the same basic principle of defining rules with targets, dependencies, and recipes. Thus, the learning curve is fairly gentle for users already familiar with Make and/or Python. In particular, Snakefile scripts use a domain-specific language (DSL) that extends Python, enabling easy customization of workflow logic. A Snakefile that reimplements our first toy example might look as follows:

```
1 from glob import glob # Import Python library
2
3 rule all:
4     input: figure.pdf
5
6 rule merge:
7     input:
8         samples = glob("sample_*.csv"),
9         script = "merge_data.py"
10    output:
11        "merged.csv"
12    shell:
13        "python {input.script} -in {input.samples} -out {output}"
14
15 rule plot:
16     # code omitted for brevity but analogous to above
```

The workflow can be executed with `snakemake -c1` (the flag specifies the number of CPU cores). To give an idea of more advanced features, we can easily modify this workflow to improve reproducibility. For example, we can specify (globally or per rule) a virtual environment using a [Docker](#) image or a [Conda](#) environment. Assuming the latter, we add the `conda` directive to our rule as follows:

```
6 rule merge:
7     conda:
8         "environment.yaml" # file that lists all necessary Python packages
```

Depending on our use case, we can specify a different environment for the `plot` rule or reuse the same one. To run this workflow, we add the `--sdm conda` (software deployment method) flag to our execution command. Snakemake will automatically build (if not available) and activate the Conda environment at runtime. If every rule specifies a Conda environment, the entire workflow can be containerized with the `--containerize` flag, which outputs a Dockerfile. After building the corresponding image and uploading it to a registry, the workflow can be executed in a container that includes all the necessary Conda environments. To do so, we add the `containerized` directive at the top of our Snakefile:

```
1 containerized: "docker://username/myworkflow:1.0.0"
```

Finally, let's imagine our scripts take a long time to execute, so we wish to run this workflow on an HPC cluster overnight. Assuming that the cluster uses SLURM,² we can reuse the same Snakefile and simply modify the execution command:

```
1 snakemake --jobs 1 \
2     --sdm apptainer conda \ # runs our job in a container with conda
3     --executor slurm \ # must be installed from snakemake plugin catalog
4     --profile my_profile # directory with config.yaml run configuration
```

²To use SLURM with Snakemake, we need the corresponding [plugin](#). Plugins for other executors are also available.

Nextflow

To give an example of a workflow manager with a different design philosophy from Make, we will introduce [Nextflow](#) (Di Tommaso et al., 2017). Rather than pre-computing a DAG, Nextflow uses a *dataflow* model inspired by the Unix | (pipe) operator. In this model, *processes* act as consumers and/or producers of data flows, communicating through unidirectional *channels*. Each process is executed in an isolated environment with automated caching (Snakemake also uses isolated environments, but caching must be enabled by the user). Crucially, processes are initiated at the same time but only start executing once they receive input through their channels. Thus, the effective execution order is not known in advance, but is still implicitly defined by the dependencies. To illustrate this, we will reimplement our original example in Nextflow. Syntaxwise, Nextflow uses a Groovy-like DSL that can make full use of the Java and Groovy standard libraries. The workflow is defined in a script with the Nextflow file extension, e.g., `main.nf`.

```
1 // Construct channels
2 samples = Channel.fromPath("data/sample_*.csv").collect()
3 merge_script = Channel.value(file("merge_data.py"))
4 plot_script = Channel.value(file("plot_figure.py"))
5
6 // Define processes
7 process MERGE {
8     publishDir("results")
9     input:
10         path(samples)
11         file(merge_script)
12     output:
13         file("merged.csv")
14     script:
15         """
16         python ${merge_script} -in ${samples.join(' ')} -out merged.csv
17         """
18 }
19
20 process PLOT {
21     // code omitted for brevity but analogous to above
22 }
23
24 // Must explicitly connect processes
25 workflow {
26     MERGE(samples, merge_script)
27     PLOT(MERGE.out, plot_script)
28 }
```

After invoking the workflow with the command `nextflow run main.nf`, the two processes MERGE and PLOT are initiated, waiting to receive input. MERGE receives its input immediately from the channels `samples` and `merge_script` and starts to execute. After it is done, the output is passed to the PLOT process, allowing it to execute. As the dataflow model makes it impossible to know in advance how many processes will be executed, we cannot perform a dry run to validate our workflow. Instead, we can use a small test data set or append our processes with *stub* (dummy) commands, which replace the real commands when the workflow is invoked with the `-stub` option. As with our Snake-make example, this workflow can be easily adapted to use Conda environments, containers, and HPC executors.

At this point, the advantages of the dataflow model may not be immediately apparent. However, when we consider a particularly complex workflow with thousands of samples and deeply nested processes, *a priori* computation of the DAG can incur substantial overhead before the workflow itself is initiated. In contrast, the dataflow model allows the workflow to run immediately, with downstream processes simply waiting to receive input.

Workflow registries

One of the advantages of workflow managers is the standardization of portable, reproducible pipelines that are easy to share. For example, Nextflow maintains a registry of community-curated open-source workflows known as [nf-core](#) (Ewels et al., 2020). Workflows can be run directly from the command line with only a base install of Nextflow; all dependencies are pulled automatically. For example, the RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq) workflow depicted in Fig. C in the Appendix can be executed with:

```
1 nextflow run nf-core/rnaseq # further arguments omitted for brevity
```

Snakemake also maintains a registry known as the [workflow catalog](#). The catalog automatically tracks Snakemake workflows hosted on GitHub and features a list of standardized workflows that adhere to additional formatting requirements. Workflows can be deployed either by cloning the respective repository from Github or by using the [SnakeDeploy](#) command line tool. For example, the RNA-Seq workflow depicted in Fig. B can be executed with:

```
1 snakedeploy deploy-workflow https://github.com/snakemake-workflows/rna-seq-  
  kallisto-sleuth . --tag v2.11.1  
2 snakemake --cores all --sdm conda
```

Selecting a workflow manager

In addition to the three tools introduced in this text, there is a [profusion](#) of alternative options available, many of which are tailored to specific domains and use cases. For example, the [targets](#) package from the [rOpenSci](#) project is a Make-like workflow manager geared toward workflows running exclusively in R. The [Galaxy Project](#) is a web-based workflow system for non-programmers. Although the graphical interface and access to free (albeit resource-limited) public servers with pre-installed workflows lower the technical barrier to entry, they also limit user customization. Conversely, deploying a custom Galaxy instance on a local cluster offers greater flexibility, but involves substantial administrative efforts. The [Common Workflow Language](#) (CWL) is an example of a *workflow specification language* that does not execute workflows directly. Rather, YAML scripts written using the CWL specification can be readily ported to various *workflow engines* such as [toil](#) to be executed on different platforms. Although CWL is designed for a high degree of interoperability, its purely declarative nature can result in verbose syntax and reduced flexibility compared to DSL-based alternatives.

With such an abundance of options, choosing the right manager for a given project can seem daunting. This primer introduced Make as a foundational automation tool to illustrate commonly encountered workflow concepts and demonstrate its utility for simple workflows such as report automation. However, its limitations render it an unlikely candidate for computationally demanding scientific workflows. Snakemake and Nextflow are viable alternatives that ensure superior reproducibility, portability, scalability, and flexibility. We encourage users to experiment with different options and choose the one that best suits their needs and preferences.

Further resources

- [The Turing Way: Reproducibility with Make](#) (Community, 2021)
- [FAIR Computational Workflows](#) (Wilkinson et al., 2025)
- [Streamlining data-intensive biology with workflow systems](#) (Reiter et al., 2021)
- [Reproducible, scalable, and shareable analysis pipelines with bioinformatics workflow managers](#) (Wratten et al., 2021)
- [Using prototyping to choose a bioinformatics workflow management system](#) (Jackson et al., 2021)

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Conceptualization, writing – original draft, software: [Peter Degen](#). Writing – review & editing: [Christian Meesters](#), [Gorka Fraga-González](#), [Samuel Pawel](#), and [Fabio Molo](#).

Appendix

Table 1: Comparison of workflow managers introduced in this text. Information as of July 2, 2025.

<i>Project</i>	GNU Make	Snakemake	Nextflow
Free and open source	✓	✓	✓
License	GPLv3	MIT	Apache 2.0
Initial release	1988	2012	2013
Primary purpose	Software building	Data analysis	Data analysis
Documentation	Here	Here	Here
Repository	Savannah	GitHub	GitHub
GitHub Stars / Contributors	N/A	2'516 / 357	2'969 / 209
<i>Platform support</i>			
Linux and macOS	✓	✓	✓
Windows	WSL ³	WSL or native (limited)	WSL
Containers	Manual	✓	✓
HPC	✗ ⁴	✓ ⁵	✓ ⁵
Cloud	✗ ⁴	✓ ⁵	✓ ⁵
<i>Building workflows</i>			
Syntax	Shell-based DSL	Python-based DSL	Groovy-based DSL
Package managers	Manual	Conda, Spack, ⁶ Modules	Conda, Spack, Modules
Containerize workflow	✗	--containerize	✗
Workflow registry	✗	Workflow catalog	nf-core
<i>Running workflows</i>			
Model	Pre-computed DAG	Pre-computed DAG	Dataflow
Selective rebuilding	Auto (timestamps)	Auto (metadata)	-resume (metadata)
Mark outputs as up-to-date⁷	-t	-t	✗
Parallelization schemes	Basic ⁸	Advanced ⁹	Advanced ⁹
Ignore failed step	-k	-k	Specify in process
Retry failed step	✗	--retries=1	Specify in process
<i>Inspecting workflows</i>			
Dry run	-n	-n	✗ ¹⁰
HTML report	✗	--report	-with-report
Visualize DAG	makefile2graph	--dag	-with-dag

³Windows Subsystem for Linux. Alternatively, a Windows implementation of Make can be used ([Make for Windows](#)).

⁴While Make can be run in cluster/cloud environments, it does not offer built-in integration with job schedulers.

⁵A list of supported executors can be found [here](#) for Snakemake and [here](#) for Nextflow.

⁶Via corresponding [plugin](#)

⁷Useful if a dependency has been trivially modified in a way that should not trigger rebuilds.

⁸Shared memory parallelization (SMP) without resource tracking.

⁹SMP, MPI, GPU with resource tracking.

¹⁰Use small data set or stub commands for run validation.

Figure A: DAG of our example Makefile created with the third-party tool [makefile2graph](#).

Figure B: Snakemake-generated rulegraph of the [Kallisto-Sleuth](#) RNA-Seq workflow. The rulegraph is a less verbose alternative to the DAG.

Figure C: RNA-Seq workflow provided by nf-core. Raw data is passed through dozens of tools to perform quality control of samples and a range of specialized tasks. Image sourced from the [nf-core/rnaseq](#) GitHub repository, licensed under the MIT License.

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